

Managing the Social Determinants of Food Choices of Rural Women in Abia State for Sustainable Living

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Abstract

The study examined the social determinants of food choices of rural women in Abia state. Three research questions guided the study. Using survey research design, the study adopted the multistage sampling technique to derive 400 respondents drawn from two major clans in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia state. The study used semi-structured questionnaire titled Food Choices of Rural Women Questionnaire (FCRWQ) to collect data. The validity and reliability of the instrument were established. The data obtained was analyzed using simple statistical tools of frequency, percentages, and mean. Findings indicated that factors that influence rural women's food choices included education (m= 3.5), location (m=3.4), time pressure (m=3.4), income (m=3.4) and social relationship (m=3.4). Data further revealed that the influence of improper food choices on rural women include stress (m=3.3) which is often triggered by emotional distress, over-labor; inferiority complex (m=3.3), concern for physical appearance (m=3.3) and health challenges (anemia and obesity, m=3.3). As a way of managing these factors, the women agreed that they would like to have more time to prepare healthy food (m=3.2); more access to fresh and healthy food (m=3.2), knowledge about good food choices (m=3.3) and food affordability, eat more fruits and vegetables in the diet and lessen the consumption of sugary snacks (m=3.4). Consequently, the study concluded that the food choices of rural women impact life and general well-being. The study therefore recommended that government should ensure the subsidization of the prices of food so that it can be within the reach of even the poorest members of the community and Home Economists should extend the knowledge of food choices and eating right to the rural farm communities through workshops and mass media enlightenment.

Keywords: Food Choices, Health and well-being, Rural Women, Social Determinants, Sustainable living

Introduction

Food choices have an impacted by the environment in so many ways like climate change, land, water, and energy use, as well as in biodiversity. According to Ferrao, Guine, Correia, & Ferreira, (2020), these factors may have several negative consequences for human well-being. The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO,2012) states that, sustainable diets correspond to diets with low environmental impact that contribute to food and national security, as well as a healthy life for both present and future generation. These diets are protective and considers biodiversity and

the ecosystems. These diets areculturally acceptable, accessible, economically, nutritional, safe, and healthy, while optimizing natural and human resources (FAO, 2012). Food choice is determined by many factors, such as education, income, location, time pressures and cultural and the social determinants that impact food related decisions among rural women. Education is an important determinant in food access, choice and eating behaviors (Owen & Nguyen, 2016), because it provides the basic food- and nutrition-related knowledge required to make informed food choices and

live a healthy life (AIHW 2012). In demonstrating this relationship, Owen & Nguyen (2016), note that the consumption of a low-fat diet is higher among those with higher education. Similarly, those with higher educational attainments consume more fruits and vegetables than those with lower educational attainments. There are indications suggesting that individuals from lower socio-economic class compared to those of higher socio-economic status are more likely to consume high fat diets, low in micronutrient density and lower intake of fruit and vegetables (Davey Smith & Bruner, 1997; Hardcastle & Blake, 2016). Hence, food access, choice, purchase, and consumption largely depend on family purchasing power.

Geographic location also influences the cost and availability of foods; as a result, people's ability to access, buy and consume healthy foods is significantly affected. Generally, the cost of a healthy diet is higher in rural and remote areas compared to urban areas (AIHW, 2012). Due to prices associated with transport, distribution and lack of demand and competition, the cost of basic nutritional foods is about 30 per cent higher in remote areas, with larger differences in the price of healthy foods (Owen & Nguyen, 2016). Fresh food is also limited, restricting food choice, and creating a barrier to a variety of fresh produce' (AIHW 2012). Another noticeable factor that affects food choice is time constraints. Contento (2011) mentioned that people have less time and will sacrifice time spent on preparing meals by buying premade food. Pelletier and Laska (2012) found that diet-related behaviors of women and students with low socio-economic status were more negatively influenced by time constraints. Family, friends, and relationship commitments have been found to place more time pressure on women, eighty three percent (83%) likely to perceive themselves as having more time constraints, which in turn affect healthy eating habits (Pelletier & Laska 2012). Lawrence & Baker (2009) explains that consumers exist within the contexts formed by other individuals and groups, such as family, friends, food industries and governments; thus, social

relationships, such as those with parents, spouses, and children, often determine food choices made by individuals. Usually, women are affected by life transitions, such as leaving home, living with a partner, or having children. Families and households provide one of the most important sets of interpersonal relationships influencing food choice. It has been reported that when women move in with a partner, their food choices become constrained by the man's preferences (Brown & Miller, 2002). Consequently, eating has the potential to create disagreement and to influence the health of both partners, although women tend to do most of the shopping for food and engage in preparation, the preferences of men and children in the home are primary influences on the food choices (Lawrence & Baker, 2009). It is based on this, that the study investigates the social determinants of food choices of rural women in Abia state for sustainable living.

A good understanding of women's stance toward healthy eating and the reasons underlying the food choices they make is important to improve feeding practices. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (2019) and Owolabi, Banjoko, Adekanmbi, Amusa & Owolewa (2020), specific recommendations for a healthy diet include consumption of more fruit, vegetables, legumes, nuts and grains and the reduction in intake of salt, sugar and fats and choosing unsaturated fats, instead of saturated fats and towards the elimination of trans-fatty acids, however, efforts to improve health behaviors within the family have been less successful in reaching people with low economic status (Attree, 2005; Emmons, 2000). According to Hardcastle & Blake (2016), reports that little efforts have been made to assist people of lower socio-economic class, hence, this study aims to address the influence of food choices of women in rural areas. The issues facing women are important because women are traditionally more involved with food purchase and preparation. To understand issues such as food choices, qualitative methods are more suitable especially when there is little existing knowledge (Hardcastle,

Glasse, Tye, & Hagger, 2015). Thus, this study contributes to the research base by exploring the factors affecting food choice made by women living in rural areas in Abia state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What are the factors that influence the food choices of rural women in Abia state?
2. What is the influence of improper food choices on women sustainable living in Abia state?
3. What are the ways to improve on the food choices of rural women in Abia state?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted the survey method.

Population of the Study

The population is made up of 400 respondents drawn from two local governments - Ikwuano Local Government Area in Abia Central Senatorial district and Umunneochi in Abia North Senatorial district of Abia state. Ikwuano is made up of four major clans: Ibere, Oboro, Ariam-Ushaka and Oloko; while Umunneochi comprise three septs: Umuchieze, Nneato and Isuochi. It is important to note that both local governments were selected because they are largely dominated by households, whose livelihood is partly or entirely dependent on agriculture. Rural women in this part of the state are mostly engaged in farming and small-scale business.

Sample Size/Sampling Technique

Simple random sampling was used to select four clans out of the seven clans. To avoid bias, the researcher deployed fish basket method and randomly picked Oboro and Ariam-Ushaka from Ikwuano, and Umuchieze and Isuochi from Umunneochi. From the four clans comprising fifty-six

villages, ten villages were selected, while in the third stage, households were selected from each village for the distribution of the questionnaires. Multistage sampling technique was also used in each stage. 400 respondents made the sample of the study.

Method of Data Collection

A semi-structured questionnaire titled Social Food Determinants Questionnaire (SFDQ) was developed by the researcher. The test items elicited responses based on the research questions. To ensure validity of the instruments, face and content validity was established. A four point scale of preference indicating SA (4), A (3), SD (2) and D (1) was used for the test items.

Two research assistants who doubled as interpreters were trained to distribute and retrieve 400 questionnaires. These assistants helped with the translation of the content of the questionnaire to some of the respondents who found it difficult to communicate in English language. The retrieval of the questionnaires witnessed 100% collection rate as the researchers were on hand to collect within the two weeks which the distribution lasted.

Method of Data Analysis

The data gathered were analyzed quantitatively using frequency, percentages and means score. The midpoint mean for weighted mean is 2.50 for any score above this mid-point was accepted, while all scores below the mid-point mean was rejected.

Results

The results are presented on tables 1-3. Table 1 shows the factors that influence the food choices of rural women. The mean sum of 3.5 agreed that education is a determinant factor of food choices among rural women x of 3.4 had a considered income/ cost, while x 3.4 agreed that social relationship affected women's choice of food just as 3.3 observed that time pressure was a factor to healthy eating. Similarly, 3.3 said location further constituted a challenge to food choices.

Table 1: Factors that Influence the Food Choices of Rural Women in Abia State

S/N	Test items	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)	Mean(x)	Decision
1	Education	255 (63.5%)	94 (23.5%)	17 (4.3%)	34 (8.5%)	3.5	Accept
2	Income	232(58%)	116(29%)	29(7.25%)	23(5.7%)	3.4	Accept
3	Geographic Location	214(53.5)	114(28.5%)	28(7%)	44(11%)	3.3	„
4	Time Pressure	245(61.2)	117(29.2)	13(3.2)	25 (6.3%)	3.3	„
5	Social Family relationship	231(57.7)	122(30.5%)	27(6.7%)	20(5%)	3.4	„

Results in Table 2 revealed that the mean sum of 3.3 agreed that they suffer from stress triggered by emotional distress; 3.3 said they suffer from inferiority complex; mean of 3.3 indicate concern

about r body image, while health challenges, mostly anemia and obesity were influenced by improper food choices.

Table 2: Influence of Improper Food Choices on Women in Abia State

S/N	Item	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)	Mean (X)	Decision
1	Stress triggered by emotional distress, over labor	223 (56%)	105 (26%)	39 (9.7%)	32 (8%)	3.3	Accept
2	Inferiority Complex	240(60%)	90 (22.5%)	39 (9.7%)	31 (7.7%)	3.3	„
3	Body Image (skin, hair)	232(58%)	93 (23%)	50 (12.5%)	25 (6.2%)	3.3	„
4	Health challenges (malnutrition, deficiency in calcium, obesity, anemia)	238 (59.5%)	82 (20.5%)	43 (10.7%)	37 (9.2%)	3.3	„

As a way of ensuring sustainable food choices, responses in table 4 indicate that the sum of 3.2 would like to have more time to prepare healthy food; 3.2 said having more access to fresh and healthy food will

improve their food choices; 3.3 said they will like to have more knowledge about sustainable food choices, and lastly (3.4) said being able to afford and eat more fruit and vegetables will improve their choices of diet.

Table 3: Ways To Improve On the Food Choices Of Rural Women In Abia State

S/N	Item	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)	Mean (x)	Decision
1	Being able to afford and eat more fruits and vegetables	231(57.7%)	117(29.9%)	35 (8.7%)	17 (4.2%)	3.4	Accept
2	Having access to fresh and healthy foods	203(50.7%)	114 (28.5%)	55 (13.7%)	28 (7%)	3.3	„
3	Having more knowledge about sustainable food choices	220 (55%)	123(30.7%)	34 (8.5%)	23 (5.7%)	3.3	„
4	Having more time to prepare good meals	212(53%)	113(28.2%)	46 (11.5%)	29 (7.2%)	3.2	„

Discussion of Findings

Findings in Table 1 indicate that the mean sum of 3.5 agreed that education is one of the determinants of food choices among rural women as knowledge concerning nutrition appeared to be an issue. For instance, one of the respondents specifically admitted her preference for spices and tomato paste with high number of colorants to make her food appear attractive, without knowing the health implication. Similarly, some of the respondents noted that food enriched with local seasonings like 'okpehi' and 'ogiri' is good but complain of the family may not like the aroma. This finding aligns with AIHW (2012) that pointed out that the lack of nutritional knowledge, as well as the knowledge required to successfully budget, plan and cook meals often predispose people to eat poor quality meals.

Sweeting & West (2005) revealed that children eat less healthily, and snacking are associated with greater deprivation and lower maternal education. Secondly, results show that majority of the women (3.4) tend to forego the healthy and more readily available foods because of cost. The food preferences within the family favor the cheaper food. Food insecurity is a challenge coupled with other competing demands on income, therefore, food choice is critical for good health. This study

buttresses earlier research that recognizes cost as a major influence on family food purchases, thus, having lower socio-economic status and being poor are strongly related to consuming inadequate diet (Shelton, 2005), particularly where food insecurity exists, and women make trade-offs between personal health and that of children (Olson, 2005).

In addition, social relationship affects women's choice of food as some of the respondents agreed that their husbands usually demand for foods that can carry them for longer hours especially those who are predominantly farmers. This finding is consistent with the position of Bargiota, Delizona, Tsitouras, Georgios, & Koukoulis (2013), who note that eating is a social event and as such, the presence of family and friends inevitably can affect food choices.

With regards to the influence of improper food choices on women, results in Table 3 revealed that (x3.3) agreed that they suffer from stress, which is triggered by emotional distress, over-labor. This is in line with the position of Owolabi et al (2020), who points out that preservatives, food colorings and other additives may

cause or worsen certain health conditions. Also, the women were often concerned about their looks (body image), (3.3), particularly the appearance of their skin, and lastly health challenges (3.3), mostly anemia and obesity. This agrees with Owolabi et al (2020) who notes that inadequate lead to diseases like bulimia, dental caries, anorexia nervosa, anemia, and accumulation of excess calories in the body causing obesity. Also, Steptoe, Perkins-Porras & McKay (2003) report that having good food-management skills is a positive influence on food choices. Having limited skill and experience with food undermines women's ability to feed the family well (Lawrence, Skinner & Haslam, 2008).

As a way of achieving sustainable food choices for women, responses in Table 4 indicate that having more time to prepare healthy food; access to fresh and healthy food, knowledge about sustainable food choices, and being able to afford and eat more fruit and vegetables will improve food choices.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The ability to make healthy food choices is considered beneficial not only for long-term health implications but also for the general well-being of an individual. Hence, this study examined the social factors that influences the food choices made by rural women. In the period of food insecurity where the prices of food items are exorbitant, it takes the knowledge of good food choice, selection, and preparation to be able to achieve food security at the rural farm levels. Based on findings, this study recommends as follows:

1. enlightenment programs like hands-on cookery, using forums like women meetings, organizations, associations, groups, and age-grades, women should be educated by Home Economics extensionists on sustainable food choices and the nutritional benefits.
2. Women should learn to patronize local farmers, grow their own foods, and further pay attention to food preparation to avoid wastage.

3. Government should ensure the subsidization of food prices so that it can be within the reach of even the poor in the community.

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